

CNTS AND NHA AS REINFORCEMENT TO IMPROVE FLEXURAL AND IMPACT PROPERTIES OF UHMWPE NANOCOMPOSITES FOR HIP JOINT APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Nano materials with their unique properties achieve good improvement when they used to reinforce polymer matrix composites. CNTs and nHA were added to matrix of UHMWPE to produce eight nanocomposites by adding four weight fractions (%) involve 1, 2, 3 and 5% of each material.

Some mechanical properties were tested in this research include the Flexural strength & Shear strength which indicated that UHMWPE/3%CNTs gave the highest strength followed by UHMWPE/5%nHA. Also the results showed that the highest impact strength was for UHMWPE/3%nHA followed by UHMWPE/3%CNTs. This improvement in these tested properties is due to the filling the pores in nanocomposites compared with pure UHMWPE which has many holes filled by air which decrease the mechanical properties of the later.

Keyword: Hip joint replacement, Acetabular cup, Nanocomposite, UHMWPE, Nano additives, Flexural, Impact.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, incorporation of nanofillers like nano particles, nano clays, nano tubes, nano fibers, etc., to produce polymer nanocomposites with mechanical and thermal barrier properties in conjunction with noticeable improvements in adhesion, rheological and processing behavior. Better dispersion of nano fillers within the matrix achieves high performance for these nanocomposites for bioapplications and structural applications [1-4]. This improvement may be due to the ratio of surface area (A) of reinforcement to volume of reinforcement (V) as suggested

by McCrum et al.[5] and the behavior of nano fillers also enhancing the interfacial properties of composites [6-7].

UHMWPE represents thermoplastics resin used in engineering field with good properties such as impact strength, biocompatibility, high wear resistance, and low friction in addition to nontoxic; thus, it is the best choice for load-bearing surface material in total joint replacement prostheses, electronics devices, engineering bearings, and other industries. The modification of UHMWPE to enhance its mechanical properties is currently a most research topic.

In this work, the effect of reinforcing by CNTs and nHA has been investigated to improve flexural and impact properties of UHMWPE nanocomposites that used as alternative material for acetabular cup of artificial hip joint.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials and Methods

Ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) from (MAX PIPE INDUSTRY Co. Ltd) with average molecular weight (5.5×10^6 g/mol), density (0.935 g/cm³) and average particle size of (20-50 μ m) was used as matrix to prepared eight nanocomposites. These nanocomposites were reinforced with four weight fraction (%) of each carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and nanohydroxyapatites (nHA).

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) (>95%, with an average diameter (30-80 nm) and lengths of 10 - 30 μ m) were syntheses via AAO templates as describes in our previous paper [8], while nano hydroxyapatite (nHA) was supplied as a nano-particles from (Merck, Darmstad, Germany Company) with average particle size (80 nm).

Four weight fractions include 1, 2, 3 and 5% of each nano additives to produce nanocomposites that prepared by weighing of chosen nano fillers (CNTs and nHA) to reinforce polymer matrix UHMWPE and mixed with 30 mL of ethanol and then stirred the mixture by hot magnetic stirrer for 45 min and 60 °C to disperse the additive in solution. The final mixture (Ethanol + Additive + UHMWPE) was put in siliphon paper and input inside dry oven for 20 min at 60 °C, after draying it left in atmospheric for 72 hrs. to evaporate the residual ethanol.

The hydraulic hot press was used to fabricate UHMWPE nanocomposites. After the previous steps, final produced mixture was put in hot plate of hydrolic press with temperature range of (195-200 °C) and then pressed under 12 MPa for 1.5 hrs at polymer Dep.in material colloge, Babylon unversity. Cooling the molds were done in air to room temperature to get specimens and then they cut by CNC laser machine according to international standard specifications for each test in this research which agreement with ASTM standard.

2.2 Properties Measurement

2.2.1 Flexural Test

The flexural test was performed according to (ASTM D790) with dimensions of specimens as shown in Fig. (1). All data measured for three points bending using the tensile machine at across head speed (strain rate) of (5 mm/min) and the load was applied is equal (5 KN) until break the specimen occurs.

Figure 1 Specimens to flexural test

The modulus of elasticity can be calculated by the following equation:

$$E_B = \frac{FL^3}{4bd^3\delta} \quad (1)$$

where: E_B is Flexural modulus (MPa), F is applied load (N), L is support span (mm), b is width of specimen (mm), d is thickness of specimen (mm) and δ is the deflection of the beam with maximum of the neutral axis and zero at the outer surface of the beam (mm). While the flexural strength ($F.S.$ in MPa) can be calculated by the following formula:

$$F.S = \frac{3PL}{2bd^2} \quad (2)$$

where: P is fracture load (N). Also flexural strain (ϵ_f as %) may be calculated as follow [9-10]:

$$\epsilon_f = \frac{6Dd}{L^2} \quad (3)$$

where: D is maximum deflection of specimen (mm).

2.2.2 Maximum Shear Strength Test

The shear test was achieved according to (ASTM D2344), see Fig. (2). All data measured for three points bending test using Hydraulic press type (Leypoldt Harris No. 36110) and can be used short beam and gradually load applied.

Figure 2 Specimens to shear strength test

2.2.3 Impact Test

Impact test was done by (ISO-180) using Izod impact test machine type (XJU series pendulum Izod/Charpy impact testing machine). For the impact test, the specimen was clamped at one end and held vertically cantilevered beam and it has broken at impact energy of (5.5 J) of pendulum and impact velocity (3.5 m/s). This test was done without notch in specimens. Izod impact is

defined as the kinetic energy needed to initiate fracture and continue the fracture until the specimen is broken. The dimensions of specimens are shown in Fig. (3).

Figure 3 Specimens to impact test.

The impact strength (G_c in J/m^2) can be calculated by depending on the energy expenditure (U_c in J) to fracture of specimen, which was measured through the test device and using flexural modulus (E_B) that obtained from flexural test as follow[13,14]:

$$G_c = \frac{U_c}{A} \quad (4)$$

where: A is the cross sectional area of specimen (m^2). While and fracture toughness (K_c in N/mm^2) can be calculated by following equation [15,16]:

$$K_c = \sqrt{G_c E_B} \quad (5)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Flexural Strength of UHMWPE Nanocomposites

Figure (4) shows the relationship between the weight fraction of additives (nHA and CNT) and flexural strength of nanocomposites. In this relationship can be seen an improvement of flexural strength for nanocomposite and the addition of CNTs has more effect on flexural strength compared with the addition of nHA with little exception. Increasing the weight fraction of nHA led to increasing flexural strength, while weight fraction of CNTs led to increasing flexural strength up to 3% and then little decreasing can occurs due to the agglomeration for CNTs at 5% [17]

Figure 4 Flexural strength of UHMWPE nanocomposites
With different additives

Generally, the presence of nano additives hinder the crack propagation inside UHMWPE matrix according to strengthening mechanism moreover to the strong bonding between the polymer matrix UHMWPE and these nano additives (CNTs and nHA) [18]

The flexural strength was increased from (0.0285 MPa) to (0.0463 MPa) for (UHMWPE/3%CNTs) and to (0.037 MPa) for (UHMWPE/3%nHA) and it continuous to became (0.0382 MPa) with 5% wt., while decreases to (0.0345 MPa) for 5% CNTs addition. In general, the structure of tube gives impedance to flexural more than that for particles (i.e., hydroxyapatite).

Figure (5) shows the relationship between the weight fraction of (CNTs and nHA) with flexural modulus of nanocomposites. It can be noticed that the values of flexural modulus increased with increasing of the weight fraction of nHA particles. This is due to the strengthening mechanism and the nature of bonding between nanomaterials and polymer matrix (UHMWPE), also this increase may be due to the fact of high flexural modulus value of the (nHA) itself compared with UHMWPE matrix. While in case of CNTs the increasing of flexural modulus contentious up to 3% and then decrease with 5% CNTs because of agglomeration.

Figure 5 Flexural modulus of UHMWPE Nanocomposites With different additives.

Figure (6) shows the relationship between the weight fraction of (CNTs and nHA) and flexural strain of nanocomposites. It can be noticed that the values of flexural strain increased with increasing of the weight fraction of two reinforcements and the addition of nHA gave higher values compared with CNTs due to the mechanical properties of each additive, but the reduction of value with 5% nHA is attributed to the agglomeration which occurs with higher concentration of addition.

Figure 6 Flexural strain of UHMWPE Nanocomposites With different additives.

Generally, the addition of CNTs and nHA gave the same behavior for flexural strength, flexural modulus and flexural strain.

3.2 Maximum Shear Stress of UHMWPE Nanocomposites

Figure (7) shows the relationship between the weight fraction of (CNTs and nHA) in UHMWPE nanocomposites with maximum shear stress values. It can be seen that the adding of CNT gave higher values compared with the adding of nHA to the polymer matrix UHMWPE. Also, increasing the weight fraction of additive led to increasing of maximum shear stress except with 5% CNTs due to agglomeration. The increasing in maximum shear stress for nanocomposites may be due to the higher bond strength that may occur between the nano additives and matrix. The increasing in maximum shear stress was from (0.71 MPa) for pure UHMWPE polymer to (1.1623 MPa) for (UHMWPE/3%CNTs) and to (0.956 MPa) for (UHMWPE/5%nHA) composite.

Figure 7 Max. Shear Stress of UHMWPE Nanocomposites with different additives.

3.3 Impact Strength and Fracture Toughness of UHMWPE Nanocomposites

The impact test is one of essential dynamic mechanical tests, Fig. (8) shows the relationship between the weight fraction of (CNTs and nHA) as reinforcement in UHMWPE matrix and impact strength. It can be observed that the values of impact strength increased with increasing of the weight fraction of both additives up to 3% and followed by little decreasing at 5% due to agglomeration. The increment in impact strength is due to the hardness and strong in the ability of resistance to impact load of nano additives comparing with pure UHMWPE matrix. The impact strength reaches to (0.0312) and (0.0325) kJ.m^{-2} when added 3% CNTs and 3% nHA respectively compared with impact strength in absence of additives (0.0015) kJ.m^{-2} . While increasing the concentration to 5% was decreased impact strength to (0.0225) and (0.0237) kJ.m^{-2} for CNTs and nHA respectively. Dispersion of nHA particles within matrix gave more strength to impact compared with the presence of hollow tubes in polymer matrix which may be left some voids in produced nanocomposites.

Figure 8 The impact strength for UHMWPE Nanocomposites with different additives.

Other behavior can be observed in Fig. (9) for the relationship between the weight fraction (%) of additives (CNTs and nHA) and the fracture toughness of UHMWPE nanocomposites. The value of fracture toughness is closed in the presence of 3% of additives to reach (0.1802) for CNTs and (0.1763) for nHA, this confirms the role of nano additives to increase the toughness of polymer matrix by filling the pores in produced composites. These nano additives lead to increase impedance and hindrance the crack propagation inside the materials, and then these additives will restrict the propagation of the cracks under loads for nanocomposites.

Figure 9 The fracture toughness for UHMWPE nanocomposites with different additives.

As observed in other properties, 5% of additives lead to decreasing in the certain property because of agglomeration and the toughness was reached to be (0.1388 and 0.1609) for (UHMWPE/5%CNTs) and (UHMWPE/5%nHA) respectively. Also, the wettability and mixing process between polymer matrix UHMWPE and nano additives may be played vital role to decrease bonding force between reinforcing materials and matrix; and increase the initial area to internal defects, and then the failure may be occur in nanocomposites with lower amount of the required energy to the fracture.

4. CONCLUSION

Adding nano hydroxyapatite with four weight fractions (1, 2, 3 and 5%) to UHMWPE matrix led to increasing flexural strength, flexural modulus, flexural strain and maximum shear stress of UHMWPE nanocomposites, while adding CNTs with the same fractions increased these properties up to 3%. The improvement in these properties after reinforcing with nano additives is due to the filling the voids within the polymer matrix that gave more compact bulk composites compared with that unreinforced composite which contains holes and pores filled by air and then cause some defects in final composite. Impact strength and fracture toughness also improved by reinforcing up to 3% of each additives due to the mechanical properties of filler itself compared with pure matrix.

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